

Physicochemical Studies on Chromium(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with on Bidentate Schiff Bases

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Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of salicylidene-*o*-aminopyridine, 5 bromosalicylidene-*o*-aminopyridine and salicylidene-*o*-aminothiazole have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of analytical, infrared and electronic spectral studies. Octahedral structures for the Cr^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes and a square planar structure for the Cu^{II} complexes have been suggested. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are non-electrolytes while Cr^{III} complexes behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes.

In continuation of our earlier work on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases, we report here the preparation of Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of salicylaldehyde Schiff bases. The complexes were characterised by analytical, spectral and magnetic studies.

Results and Discussion

Physical and analytical data of the complexes and ligands are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. The copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes exhibit molar conductance below 50 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating their non-electrolytic nature while the chromium(III) complexes behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes.

Values of magnetic moments are given in Table 1. All the complexes are paramagnetic. The

observed value (~ 3.85 B.M.) in the case of Cr^{III} complexes suggests an octahedral configuration. The magnetic susceptibility values obtained for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes indicate that they have octahedral configuration¹. Magnetic moments of ~ 1.78 B.M. for the Cu^{II} complexes are suggestive of square-planar geometry.

Electronic spectra of the three Schiff bases are characterised by three high intensity bands lying at 29 000–31 000, 31 000–38 000, 43 000–48 000 cm^{-1} assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions in the ligands respectively. During the complex formation a red-shift is detected for these bands which indicates the involvement of Schiff base 'n' coordination. In addition to this, spectra of the complexes are characterised by a strong

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				Metal	Br	S
[CrL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Yellowish brown	64.20	3.84	11.08 (10.03)	—	—
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Purple	40.90	5.01	14.68 (12.04)	—	—
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Pale green	33.20	2.81	12.36 (12.00)	—	—
[CuL ₂]	Brown	20.10	1.80	13.60 (13.87)	—	—
[CrL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Brown	70.88	3.90	7.08 (7.69)	26.90 (23.65)	—
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish brown	09.19	4.73	9.60 (9.11)	24.31 (24.69)	—
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Greenish yellow	49.40	2.75	9.20 (9.07)	22.67 (24.70)	—
[CuL ₂]	Brown	24.70	1.90	10.70 (10.32)	25.79 (25.94)	—
[CrL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	Light brown	73.31	3.86	12.80 (9.77)	—	11.26 (12.05)
[CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Purple	07.44	4.87	11.73 (11.70)	—	10.42 (12.73)
[NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Greenish yellow	30.23	2.89	12.05 (11.66)	—	11.94 (12.74)
[CuL ₂]	Coffee brown	14.04	1.78	13.67 (12.45)	—	12.56 (13.58)

absorption at 25 000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the charge transfer transition from ligand to metal. The spectrum of the Cr^{III} complexes have three $d-d$ transition bands which can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions of Cr^{III} . The Ni^{II} complexes also exhibit three $d-d$ transitions in the electronic spectrum. Among these, the lowest frequency transition occurs at the end of visible region. The purple colour of $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complexes are suggestive of octahedral geometry. But the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes are characterised by two bands at 9 500–10 526 and 20 000–22 000 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. In the case of octahedral cobalt the band ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ is due to a transition of two electrons which is forbidden and gives to a weak band. And again ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ are very close in octahedral geometry. Due to these factors, detection of the middle band is very difficult.

The copper(II) complexes show only one broad medium intensity band at 12 500–16 666 cm^{-1} which may be due to the transition of $E \rightarrow T_2$ suggestive of its square planarity². It is believed that it is a composite band involving transition of electron from different occupied d -orbitals to the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals.

The three ligands L'H, L''H, L'''H exhibit sharp ir bands at $\sim 1\,620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to azomethine linkage. In all the complexes this band appears at a frequency higher than that in the free ligand. This indicates the involvement of nitrogen atom in coordination from metal to ligand³.

The characteristic ν_{OH} band (3 590–3 640 cm^{-1}) was absent in the ligands. While a broad band appears at 2 500–3 500 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the presence of intramolecular H-bonding⁴. This broad band is absent in all the complexes indicating deprotonation and coordination of the OH group. Again the phenolic (C–O) band of the uncoordinated ligand shifted to higher frequency region indicating oxygen coordination. A shift of ν_{OH} band to lower frequency and a rocking vibration occurring at 860 cm^{-1} indicate coordinated water molecules in the complexes. In all the complexes the medium to weak band at 500–540 and 350–340 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ respectively.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
L'H	Yellow	65	73.00 (72.69)	5.20 (5.08)	13.60 (14.13)
L''H	Orange red	134	51.80 (51.99)	3.10 (3.63)	9.70 (10.10)
L'''H	Brownish yellow	87	59.20 (58.80)	4.23 (3.95)	13.06 (13.72)

Characteristic stretching frequency of C=N due to amino pyridine at 1 550 cm^{-1} is present in all the complexes of aminopyridine Schiff bases. Bands at 3 100–3 400 and 860 cm^{-1} were absent in

the copper(II) complexes showing the absence of coordinated water molecules.

These studies suggest octahedral structures for the chromium(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes and a square-planar structure for the copper(II) complexes.

Experimental

The ligands salicylidene-*O*-aminopyridine (L'H), 5-bromosalicylidene-*O*-aminopyridine (L''H) and salicylidene-*O*-aminothiazole (L'''H) were prepared following general procedure⁵. These ligands were formed by the condensation of the corresponding aldehyde and amine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in distilled methanol and purified by recrystallisation from methanol (Table 2).

The complexes of Cr^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared by refluxing methanolic solutions of metal acetate/chloride and L'H, L''H and L'''H in 1 : 2 molar ratio. Sodium acetate was added in the case of the Cr^{III} and Co^{II} complexes to adjust the pH. The complexes were filtered and washed with 50% methanol.

All the complexes were analysed for metal by pyrolysis at 100–800°. Besides this cobalt and nickel were estimated using EDTA and DMG methods respectively. Volhard's method was used for the estimation of bromine, and sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO_4 .

The molar conductance of the complexes were measured in methanol at a concentration of 10^{-4} M with a Systronics 305 conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. Electronic spectra (methanol/acetone) of the complexes were measured on a Hitachi 220 spectrophotometer. Solid spectra were taken for salicylidene-*o*-aminopyridine complexes of Cr^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} . Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

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